

Experimental Seamless Virtual Machine Migration Using a SDN IT and Network Orchestrator

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Abstract: This paper demonstrates an experimental Virtual Machine (VM) migration across several network domains (intra/inter-datacenter) while the VM network connection state is maintained. A SDN IT and Network Orchestrator is responsible for the VM seamless migration.
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1. Introduction

Virtual Machine (VM) migration has been proposed in several situations to maintain the overall efficiency of the Data Center (DC) (e.g., Night/day periodic migrations, load imbalance, host failure) [1]. Different types of virtual machine migration exist, being the most common live and block migration. Live migration allows moving a VM without interrupting the processes running inside it, on the other side block migration involves a disruption service time in which the VM is stopped.

VMs do not run isolated. Typically, a VM is connected with other VMs in the same network to offer a joint service. If one of the VMs from a network is migrated, its connection state must be maintained, which is known as a VM seamless migration [2]. The migration of a virtual instance must be transparent for all the hosts connected to the virtual machine migrated (i.e., after a disruption time the connectivity between them will be recovered).

Service Function Chaining is an example from NFV where different processes running in different VMs are interconnected through the network to support a service. Seamless migration of the involved VMs is a strict requirement in order to provide the necessary Quality of Experience (QoE).

The authors in [3] have presented an integrated SDN IT and Network Orchestrator (SINO) which is capable of the establishment of end-to-end paths through heterogeneous networks. In this paper, we propose a network orchestration approach where several SDN controllers are directly orchestrated from SINO, while in [3] a single SDN controller handled the programmability of the different network domains. The presented SINO allows providing seamless migration of VMs between DCs in a multi-layer/multi-domain network scenario using a block migration strategy. This work has been validated in the Cloud Computing platform of the ADRENALINE Testbed.

2. SDN and IT network orchestration architectural overview

Fig.1.a. shows the SINO architecture, which is able to jointly deploy IT and network resources. The SINO consists of two main building blocks: Virtual IT Resource Manager (VIRM) and Network Orchestrator (NO).

The VIRM is responsible of the creation/migration/deletion of virtual instances (computing service), disk images storage (image service), and the management of the VM network interfaces (networking service). The computing service (e.g., Nova in OpenStack) is responsible of the management of the IT instances, centralizing the commands for the computing operations into the compute hosts (Hosts 1-4 in Fig. 1.a). A compute service agent is running in each host and controls the computing hypervisor (KVM) responsible of the creation/migration/deletion of the VMs. The Image Service (e.g., Glance in OpenStack) handles the disk images which are used as templates for VM file systems; it also operates in a centralized manner by maintaining a copy of all the disk images in the VIRM. An image-service agent is running in each host to request the download of images when a new VM instantiation requires it. It also permits to create new images of the currently working instances, a process known as snapshotting. Finally, the connectivity between VMs and virtual switches inside the hosts is managed by the networking service (e.g., Neutron in OpenStack). It creates the virtual interfaces, attaches them into the virtual switches and offers a DHCP service for the VMs to get the assigned IP address. The SINO controls the VIRM through a RESTful API, which is used to trigger the VIRM actions and to get the necessary information about the running VM instances.

The NO is introduced in order to support end-to-end connectivity by orchestrating the different network domains through per-domain controllers. In the proposed network architecture, the intra-DC Ethernet OpenFlow Switches (OFS) are controlled by an OpenFlow controller (i.e., OpenDaylight). The inter-DC network is a GMPLS-controlled WSON with an Active Stateful Path Computation Element (AS-PCE).

The NO (Fig.1b) architecture is based on the proposed ABNO [4]. The Topology Server is the component responsible of building the network topology which it is stored in the Traffic Engineering Databased (TED). The

Fig. 1. a) SINO architecture; b) Network Orchestrator architecture; c) VM migration scenario.

TED includes all the information about network links and nodes, and it is used by the Path Computation Element (PCE) for calculating routes across the network.

The Virtual Network Topology Manager (VNTM) is the responsible of the multilayer management. In the proposed architecture, the VNTM will arrange the set-up of an optical connection and offer it as a L2 link to satisfy the L2 connectivity demand. The Provisioning Manager implements the different provisioning interfaces to push the forwarding rules into the data plane. It is connected to the OF controller responsible of the OF domains through REST interfaces, and to the AS-PCE [5] which initiates the connections into the GMPLS-based DWDM optical network. Flow server stores the connections established in the network into a FlowDB. Finally the Orchestration Controller handles all the processes involved inside the NO to satisfy the provisioning of end-to-end connectivity.

3. Experimental validation

To validate the previously described architecture, we present the seamless migration of a virtual machine over a multi-layer/multi-domain network. In the proposed scenario the VM₁ is connected to the VM₂ both are running into the DC-1. We validate that the proposed architecture is able to provide seamless migration of VM₁ to DC-2. The experiment assesses a block migration using the inter-DC network (Fig. 1c) and measures the disruption time in which VM₂ cannot access to the VM₁. The process involves six steps, detailed in Fig. 2.a.:

1- Virtual machine migration request trigger: SINO receives a VM₁ migration request through HTTP request.

2- Deletion of VM connections: all the flows established in the network in which the target VM is involved must be removed before start the migration. The NO looks into the Flow Server database for all flows involving VM₁, the provisioning manager deletes all of them by sending the orders to the OpenDaylight controller which at once will send the OFPT_FLOW_REMOVED messages to the OFSs.

3- Inter-DC connectivity: the VIRM, the source and destination hosts must be interconnected during all the migration process in order to exchange the VM image's data. The SINO adds each of the three hosts (VIRM, Host1 and Host3) as external hosts into the NO available endpoints, and request an end-to-end path between each pair. The inter-DC connectivity between hosts involves the establishment of a Label Switched Path (LSP) into the WSON by sending a Path Computation Initiate Message to the AS-PCE.

4- IT migration: In the proposed scenario, first, the VM₁ is paused and snapshotted in the source host and it is saved into the VIRM. Once the VM₁ snapshot is ready, the VM₁ instance is removed and a new instance based in the recently created snapshot is deployed into the destination server.

5- Restore VM connections: the connections are restored between the migrated VM and all the rest of VMs to which was connected. In the proposed scenario, the new path between VM₁ and VM₂ is calculated by the NO PCE, the LSP between DCs is reused, and it is only necessary to establish the flows of the OFSs.

6- Acknowledgement of virtual machine migration: The client is notified of VM₁ successful migration.

Fig. 2. a) VM migration flow diagram; b) Wireshark capture of SINO commands; c) VM migration traffic (packets/s) received in DC2 over time; d) ICMP traffic capture between VM1 and VM2 during VM1 seamless migration.

The proposed architecture has been validated in the Cloud Computing platform of the ADRENALINE Testbed. The OpenStack Havana release has been deployed into servers with 2 x Intel Xeon E5-2420 and 32GB RAM each. Four OpenFlow switches have been deployed. Each Data Center border switch has a 10 Gb/s XFP tunable transponder and OFS. Finally, the GMPLS-controlled optical network is composed of an all-optical WSON with 2 ROADMs and 2 OXCs providing reconfigurable end-to-end lightpaths.

Fig.2.b. shows the wireshark capture at the SINO, including the commands send to the VIRM and NO. Also the commands between NO and ODL or AS-PCE are included. We can obtain this detailed capture as we are running on the same machine the SINO, VIRM, NO and ODL. In Fig. 2.c., the incoming traffic to DC-2 is shown by sampling each 5secs the packets received in the border OFS of DC-2. A significant increase of the number of packets occurs after the trigger of creation of a VM₁ into Host3 due to the download of the VM₁ image from VIRM. Finally, a traffic capture of the dialog between VM₂ and VM₁ is shown in Fig. 2.d which provides the total disruption time occurred due to the seamless migration process. We can observe that after a downtime of 158s the connectivity between VM₁ and VM₂ is recovered. It can be observed that the MAC address of VM₁ has changed due to the block migration.

4. Conclusions

In this paper we have demonstrated a VM seamless migration through multiple domains. A SINO has been used to both handle the flow reconfiguration and the VM migration, while not affecting VM network status. We have observed that a full VM migration takes about 158s. Further research might result in better time results if a make-before-break strategy and a live VM migration is considered.

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